

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES FOR TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstrac: The project approach of teaching foreign languages at universities is the subject of this essay. The project approach is defined in the article as a specifically planned, motivated learning exercise with the goal of investigating and resolving a theoretically or practically important issue. The article outlines the major phases of project activity as well as the typology of projects. The primary duties involved in carrying out project activities at the institution are also taken into account. Currently, there are several benefits to employing the project method in pedagogy over more conventional teaching approaches. Students' capacity to think constructively, their enthusiasm to study, their teamwork skills, their leadership abilities, their collaboration and self-presentation abilities—all of which are developed by working on projects.

Key words: Technology-enhanced language learning,digital tools for language teaching,gamification in language education,virtual reality in language instruction,mobile language learning apps.

INTRODUCTION

In every type of educational activity that fosters independence, self-direction, and self-regulation, modern, innovative technology provide new avenues for communication and productivity between educators and students.In order to integrate educational material, talents, knowledge, skills, and rates of absorption in the student's personality, new innovative technologies serve as the foundation. This makes it possible to employ a personality-differentiated method to teaching a foreign language.

Creating interaction in the lesson, also known as interactivity in the technique, is one of the new needs for teaching foreign languages utilizing the Internet and multimedia technology. Although this idea is not new, there is currently no universally recognized definition for it. Interactivity is defined by R.P. Milrud as the synchronization, complementarity, and unity of efforts toward a communication aim and outcome using speech methods [4]. This definition leads us to the conclusion that

one way to accomplish the communicative aim in the classroom is through the use of an interactive method in virtual space.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Not only does interactive content provide authentic scenarios, but it also compels you to answer appropriately in a foreign language. And once things start to go our way, we can discuss language proficiency. even in the event of mistakes. The capacity to react to other people's words in a spontaneous and harmonic way, expressing your sentiments and emotions while changing and reconstructing on the go, is what matters most. Therefore, we may view interaction as a means of self-improvement via the Internet: the chance to watch and mimic the language, abilities, and behavioral patterns of partners; deduce fresh insights from issues during their collaborative debate.

The topic of whether or not to include more cutting-edge technologies into the educational process has come up often in recent years. The process of computerization and the utilization of cutting-edge information technologies have made it possible for new chances to appear that assist the development of educational systems. The goal of this research is to better understand how cutting-edge technology affect foreign language instruction. Teaching foreign languages has become much more varied and enriching thanks to cutting-edge technologies. Intellectual and creative exploration takes the place of monotonous labor, resulting in the creation of a new, purposeful, and active personality that is dedicated to ongoing education and self-improvement. On the other hand, cutting-edge technologies have to be grounded in conventional teaching strategies and methodologies, which are enhanced by knowledge and advancements in science and technology.

But since this process doesn't happen by itself, the teacher in this educational process has to have training that qualifies them to transmit information and the student has to be able to detect it. However, competent improvement fulfills a new communal demand that guarantees the inventiveness of human resources rather than being a personal whim or requirement. Innovative technologies, on the other hand, enable the improvement of this process, whose primary objective is individual socialization. Computer technologies are one form of new technology that makes it possible to modify the way that foreign languages are taught. This allows students to concurrently gain distinct skills and abilities for each type of speech. As the student is learning the art of speaking, he may utter foreign language phrases into a microphone; as he is learning the phenomena of grammar, he can complete grammar exercises. In the process of hearing, the student can hear speech in a foreign

language. Pupils can compose spoken messages in a foreign language using various mediums such as essays, projects, biographies, postcards, and questionnaires. The letter serves as a "global patcher." It is now feasible to show information as text, photos, videos, or sounds thanks to modern methods of information storage. The way a curriculum is structured affects how well students are able to reason, analyze, draw conclusions, and follow fundamental laws.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Additionally, there are benefits to computer programs as supplemental aids for learning foreign languages. One such benefit is the ability to customize instruction for each learner. The instructor can modify the lesson plan based on the skills and interests of each student individually with the use of multimedia technology. The Internet is a valuable and easily available resource for relevant and genuine literature for teaching a foreign language. It also serves as a virtual repository for the foreign language culture of those who speak the language. Internet resources are used by teachers and students to plan and execute assignments, as well as to gain detailed information and apply it in future courses. In every type of educational activity that fosters independence, self-direction, and self-regulation, modern, innovative technology provide new avenues for communication and productivity between educators and students. In order to integrate educational material, talents, knowledge, skills, and rates of absorption in the student's personality, new innovative technologies serve as the foundation. This makes it possible to employ a personality-differentiated method to teaching a foreign language. Additionally, they alter a number of information and assessment functions as well as the significance of the educator and student in the teaching and learning process. This is demonstrated by the development of a new model for the design of the educational process, which actively incorporates electronic textbooks, online learning, and project-based learning. When teaching a foreign language, new and inventive technologies and telecommunications methods take on the familiarity of a tool in the teacher's hands, preparing pupils for the technologies of the future.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, I would want to point out that as the world changes every minute, so do the educational strategies and technology. Teachers need to stay current with the times and never stop improving their skills and talents if they want to help pupils acquire the traits and ways of thinking that they need.

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